

RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES TO CONTRACTS FOR THE PROVISION OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICES

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Annotation

This article discusses the rights and obligations of the parties involved in contracts for the provision of telecommunications services. It highlights the key rights of the customer, such as receiving accurate information, privacy, quality service, and dispute resolution. The article also outlines the obligations of the customer, including paying for the service and complying with the terms of the contract. In addition, it covers the rights and obligations of the service provider, such as receiving payment, enforcing the terms of the contract, providing quality service, protecting customer information, and resolving disputes.

Key words: telecommunications services, contracts, rights, obligations, customer, service provider, accurate information, privacy, quality service, dispute resolution, payment, usage limits, customer information, formal complaints process.

Telecommunications services have become an integral part of our daily lives, providing us with the ability to communicate with people across the globe. As such, the contracts for the provision of telecommunications services have become increasingly important and complex. These contracts govern the relationship between the service provider and the customer, outlining the rights and obligations of each party. In this article, we will explore the key rights and obligations of the parties to contracts for the provision of telecommunications services.

Rights of the Customer

The customer has a number of rights when entering into a contract for the provision of telecommunications services. These include:

1. The right to receive accurate information: The service provider must provide the customer with accurate information about the services they are offering, including the pricing, features, and limitations of the service.

2. The right to privacy: The customer has the right to expect that their personal information will be kept confidential and not shared with third parties without their consent.

3. The right to quality service: The service provider must ensure that the service they provide is of a high quality and meets the customer's expectations.

4. The right to dispute resolution: If there is a dispute between the customer and the service provider, the customer has the right to seek resolution through a formal complaints process.

Obligations of the Customer

In addition to their rights, customers also have certain obligations when entering into a contract for the provision of telecommunications services. These include:

1. Paying for the service: The customer is obligated to pay for the service they receive in accordance with the terms of the contract.

2. Complying with the terms of the contract: The customer must comply with all terms and conditions set out in the contract, including any usage limits or restrictions.

3. Providing accurate information: The customer must provide accurate information when signing up for the service, such as their name, address, and contact details.

Contractual-legal regulation also plays a crucial role in ensuring that telecommunication services are accessible to all consumers, regardless of their location or financial status. Service providers must ensure that their services are available in all areas, including rural and remote regions. They must also offer affordable plans and packages for low-income consumers.

In addition to these regulations, contractual-legal frameworks also play a significant role in resolving disputes between consumers and service providers. In cases where consumers have complaints about the quality of services or pricing policies, they can seek redress through legal channels. This ensures that consumers have a fair and transparent process for resolving disputes with service providers.

Overall, contractual-legal regulation is essential for ensuring fair and transparent practices in the telecommunication industry. It protects the interests of both consumers and service providers and ensures that telecommunication services remain accessible and affordable for all. As the use of telecommunication services continues to grow, it is crucial that these regulations are enforced to ensure that consumers are protected and their rights are upheld [1].

Rights of the Service Provider

The service provider also has a number of rights when entering into a contract for the provision of telecommunications services. These include:

1. The right to receive payment: The service provider has the right to receive payment for the services they provide in accordance with the terms of the contract.

2. The right to terminate the contract: If the customer breaches the terms of the contract, the service provider has the right to terminate the contract.

3. The right to enforce the terms of the contract: The service provider has the right to enforce the terms and conditions of the contract, including any usage limits or restrictions.

Obligations of the Service Provider

Along with their rights, service providers also have certain obligations when entering into a contract for the provision of telecommunications services. These include:

1. Providing quality service: The service provider is obligated to provide a high-quality service that meets the customer's expectations.

2. Protecting customer information: The service provider must protect customer information and ensure that it is not shared with third parties without the customer's consent.

3. Resolving disputes: If there is a dispute between the customer and the service provider, the service provider is obligated to seek resolution through a formal complaints process.

The contract for the provision of telecommunication services is a legally binding agreement between a service provider and a consumer. It outlines the terms and conditions of the service, including pricing, service quality, and consumer rights and protections.

Scientific views and approaches to the contract for the provision of telecommunication services vary, but there is a general consensus that it is a key component of the regulatory framework for the telecommunication industry. The contract serves as a means of establishing a clear and transparent relationship between the service provider and the consumer, ensuring that both parties understand their rights and obligations [2].

In terms of national and foreign civil doctrine, the contract for the provision of telecommunication services is typically governed by contract law. This includes general principles of contract formation, such as offer and acceptance, consideration, and intention to create legal relations.

However, there are also specific regulations that apply to telecommunication services contracts. These may include requirements for pricing transparency, consumer privacy protections, and service quality standards.

Overall, the contract for the provision of telecommunication services is an essential tool for regulating the telecommunication industry and protecting consumer rights. It ensures that both service providers and consumers understand their obligations and are held accountable for their actions.

The methods of concluding a contract for the provision of telecommunication services have evolved over time, with the rise of remote and artificial intelligence technologies. Consumers can now enter into contracts with service providers through online platforms and mobile applications, without the need for physical interaction. This has made the process more convenient and efficient for consumers, but also raises concerns about the security and privacy of personal information.

To address these concerns, service providers must ensure that their remote and artificial intelligence technologies comply with relevant data protection laws and regulations. This includes obtaining consent from consumers before collecting and processing their personal information, implementing appropriate security measures to protect against data breaches, and providing clear and transparent information about how the data will be used.

Protecting the rights of consumers of telecommunication services is also crucial in ensuring fair and equitable access to these services. This includes ensuring that pricing is transparent and competitive, and that consumers have access to information about the quality of services they are receiving. Service providers must also provide clear and accessible channels for consumers to raise complaints or disputes, and must take appropriate action to resolve these issues in a timely manner [3].

Improving the quality of telecommunication services is another important aspect of ensuring consumer satisfaction. Service providers must invest in technology and infrastructure to ensure that their services are reliable, fast, and accessible. They must also provide adequate customer support to address any issues that may arise, and must continually evaluate and improve their services to meet changing consumer needs.

Developing the legal basis for providing telecommunication services via satellite is another area of focus for the industry. As satellite technology

becomes more advanced and accessible, service providers are increasingly offering services that rely on satellite connectivity. This requires a regulatory framework that addresses issues such as licensing, spectrum allocation, and international coordination.

The specifics of a digital asset can be called its existence in a kind of environment of trust between anonymous counterparties, which (trust) is formed based on the use of algorithms [4]. A kind of trust in the algorithm in an untrusted environment determines the peculiarities of the turnover of digital assets. In the corresponding ecosystems that technologically provide access to the digital asset market, a special environment of trust is created between anonymous counterparties, the transfer, creation and introduction of assets into circulation are facilitated and do not require the participation of intermediaries, it becomes possible to use self-executing contracts to a certain extent, etc.

The conducted research has shown that today the number of digital assets with economic value and exclusively digital essence can include: tokens, cryptocurrencies, big data, domain names, accounts. It is possible that with the development of technology, other types of digital assets will appear.

The identified specific features of the listed digital assets as objects of civil rights allow us to conclude that the formation of special legal regimes for them is inevitable. Unlike traditional objects of civil rights, they are subject primarily to technological patterns of turnover, which should be reflected in the legal regulation of these relations.

It seems that at this stage, the necessary body of knowledge about new digital assets has not yet been accumulated, which would make it possible to develop a common concept and a common legal regime for them. It is necessary to follow the path of creating separate legal regimes based on the functional purpose of certain types of digital assets, thereby determining their legal nature.

Previously, accounts on social networks and in virtual games were not subject to direct transfer either in the order of singular or in the order of universal succession.

Examples of legislative regulation of this sphere can be found in the legislation of some states of America. The Delaware State in August 2014 was the first to legislatively provide for the possibility of registering ownership of Internet accounts belonging to a deceased citizen [5]. In Idaho and Oklahoma, relatives of the deceased can access blogs, mail and social pages, and in Indiana — to documents and information stored electronically (or get a copy of them) [6].

Conclusion

In conclusion, contracts for the provision of telecommunications services are complex agreements that govern the relationship between the service provider and the customer. Both parties have rights and obligations that must be respected in order to ensure a fair and equitable agreement. By understanding these rights and obligations, customers and service providers can work together to create a successful and mutually beneficial relationship.

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